

EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN AGRICULTURE

Senior teacher

Ibragimova Madina Ismoilovna

Annotation: This country highlights the importance of employment in agriculture, how it affects the development of the economy of Uzbekistan and the ways of development of agriculture.

Key words: employment, agriculture, export, industry, low-income population, agricultural sector, innovative technologies.

Employment is the activity of people that does not contradict the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is related to the satisfaction of their personal and social needs, and brings them income.

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the exclusive right to dispose of their abilities for productive and creative work and to carry out any activity not prohibited by law, including those not related to the performance of paid work.

Agriculture is a branch of the economy aimed at providing the population with food (food, food) and obtaining raw materials for a number of industries. It is important to note that agriculture is one of the most important industries in almost all countries of the world.

Economic reforms and measures taken by the government to join the World Trade Organization (WTO) will help Uzbekistan increase the export of its agricultural products, in particular fruits and vegetables, to more countries of the world.

In the modern world, the agro-food sector, which includes agriculture, food and light industry, plays a vital role in the economy of Uzbekistan. In 2019, its share in the country's GDP was the largest - 41%, and it accumulated 19% of all export

earnings. Today, agriculture alone accounts for 28% of GDP. More people work here than in any other industry - 27% of the entire workforce or more than 3.65 million citizens. Despite the severe socio-economic consequences of the coronavirus pandemic for Uzbekistan, this industry continues to be an important driver of economic growth¹.

One of the benefits of agriculture is the ability to create more jobs than is currently the case. An estimated 700,000 to 1.3 million new workers could be added to the agri-food sector through thoughtful government support and investment each year. This is more than enough to solve the problem of creating jobs for 600,000 young people who fill up the labor market throughout the country every year.

The value of agriculture lies not only in the number of jobs created here. Employment in this sector has a stronger impact on reducing poverty and inequality than in any other industry.

About 80% of the country's low-income citizens live in rural areas, and their income is almost entirely dependent on agriculture. Jobs in agriculture not only help to reduce poverty, but also increase opportunities for greater participation of the rural population in various economic processes.

Consequently, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 on the strategy of action, where the 3rd priority area includes the modernization and intensive development of agriculture. According to which the country will pay special attention to:

- strengthening the food security of the country;
- expansion of production of an environmentally friendly product;
- increasing the export potential of the agricultural sector
- further optimization of sown areas, aimed at reducing the sown areas for cotton and cereal crops, with the placement of potatoes, vegetables, fodder and oilseeds on the released lands, as well as new intensive orchards and vineyards;

¹ <https://blogs.worldbank.org/ru/europeandcentralasia/how-create-more-jobs-and-reduce-poverty-uzbekistan-focus-agri-food-sector>

- creation and introduction of new varieties of agricultural products resistant to diseases and pests, etc.

To ensure employment of the population in rural areas, special attention should be paid to the introduction of innovative technologies in the agricultural sector. At the same time, improve the skills of local workers so that they can intelligently use the limited resources of the land to grow better products for the satisfaction of society. In addition, it is necessary to create conditions for farmers to have accurate and timely data on the possibilities and requirements for products in export markets, climatic conditions, as well as technologies and methods of farming, so that they do not experience difficulties in acquiring modern agricultural machinery and equipment, and also high-quality seeds adapted to various agro-ecological conditions and resistant to climate change, which were developed by local research institutes.

List of used literature

1. Zhanobilova M.K., Makhmudova N.B. national idea. development strategy of Uzbekistan;
2. Aziz Nurbekov, Uygun Aksoy, Khafiz Muminjanov and Alisher Shukurov “Organic agriculture in Uzbekistan.
3. <https://www.lex.uz/acts/9878>
4. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/ru/europeandcentralasia/how-create-more-jobs-and-reduce-poverty-uzbekistan-focus-agri-food-sector>